

BIODEGRADATION OF TRIBUTYLTIN BY CHESAPEAKE BAY MICROORGANISMS

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ABSTRACT

We have been studying microbial resistance to butyltin compounds and the degradation of tributyltin spiked into samples of Chesapeake Bay waters. Butyltin species were identified and quantified using a gas chromatograph equipped with a tin-selective flame photometric detector (GC-FPD), providing ng/l detection limits. No biodegradation of a tributyltin spike (1 µg/l, final concentration) was detected in water samples (from Annapolis and Baltimore Harbor) collected in winter and incubated in the laboratory at the in situ temperature. However, degradation of tributyltin to dibutyltin and monobutyltin species was detected in samples collected in summer. Incubation of these samples under incandescent lamps accelerated biodegradation, suggesting the involvement of photosynthetic microorganisms. At certain times in these degradation experiments, tetrabutyltin was detected by GC-FPD and confirmed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organotin-based antifouling coatings are increasingly used worldwide by private and commercial vessels. Formulations employing the tributyltin moiety as the toxic agent are most often used¹. However, the environmental fate and effects of the leached tributyltin is not fully understood. Laboratory bioassays have shown that the tributyltin species is toxic to several species of marine life, including fish², copepods³, oyster⁴ and crab⁵ larvae and mysid shrimp⁶ at µg/l (parts per billion) and lower levels in sea water. Reported levels of tributyltin in marine and estuarine waters range from undetectable (current detection limits about 1.0 ng/l) to as much as 0.3-1.0 µg/l in heavily used harbor and marina areas^{7,8,9,10}.

The role of microorganisms in the degradation of tributyltin in marine and estuarine waters and its bioaccumulation is largely unknown. Several previous investigations, summarized in Table 1, have shown biodegradation of relatively high levels of tributyltin by pure

cultures of algae, fungi and bacteria. However, little information is available as to the rates and pathways of tributyltin degradation by natural microbial populations at environmental (parts per billion and lower) concentrations. In one reported instance, tributyltin cation was rapidly adsorbed on the cell envelope of gram-negative estuarine bacteria without biotransformation or affect on bacterial growth.¹¹

This paper describes some of our research on the occurrence of tributyltin-resistant microorganisms in Chesapeake Bay and the biodegradation of tributyltin by populations of estuarine microorganisms.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

Samples were collected from various sites in Chesapeake Bay, from docks or piers or aboard the research vessel Ridgely Warfield. Water samples were aseptically collected at approximately 1 meter depth using sterile Niskin bags (for microbial enumeration) or sterile glass bottles (for degradation experiments). Surface sediment samples were collected using a grab sampler. All samples collected aboard ship were processed immediately. Those collected from docks were transported to the laboratory at the in situ temperature and processed within 3 hours of collection. Numbered sample sites correspond to stations established by the Chesapeake Bay Institute, Shady Side, MD.

Bacterial enumeration

Samples of water or sediment were diluted in sterile tubes of artificial estuarine salts solution¹⁶, and 0.1 - 0.2 ml was spread onto the surface of an artificial estuarine salts agar medium described previously¹⁶ except made half strength with respect to organic components. Butyltin chlorides (obtained from commercial suppliers) were prepared as methanol concentrates (approximately 1000 mg/l) and were added to the warm molten agar medium prior to pouring plates. Inoculated agar plates were incubated in the dark for one week at 22°C prior to counting colonies.

TABLE 1

SOME REPORTS OF MICROBIAL DEGRADATION OF TRIBUTYLTIN

Organism	Spike	Incubation Conditions	Degradation Products		% Conversion Of Tributyltin	Ref
			major	minor		
culture filtrates of wood or cellulose degrading fungi: <u>Coniophora puteana</u> , <u>Sistotrema brinkmanii</u> , <u>Coriolus versicolor</u>	TBTO--33 mg/l	1 hr, 37°C, mineral salts, sawdust medium	Bu ₂ Sn ²⁺	BuSn ³⁺	13.5-32% Bu ₂ Sn 1.5-2.5% BuSn	13
<u>Ankistrodesmus falcatus</u> (green alga)	TBTO--20 µg/l	up to 4 weeks, 20°C, mineral salts, light	Bu ₂ Sn ²⁺	BuSn ³⁺ Sn (inorganic)	50% in 4 wks.	14
<u>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</u>	TBTO--2.5 mg/l	up to 30 d, 30°C, mineral salts or peptone glucose	BuSn ³⁺	Bu ₂ Sn ²⁺	15-20% in 10 d	15
<u>Coniophora puteana</u>	1.0 mg/l	up to 28 d, 30°C, malt extract	BuSn ³⁺ Bu ₂ Sn ²⁺	--	10-15% in 7 d	15
<u>Trametes versicolor</u>	1.0 mg/l	up to 28 d, 30°C, malt extract	BuSn ³⁺	--	50%	15

Butyltin measurements

Concentrations of butyltin species in Chesapeake Bay waters were determined by means of a combination hydridization/dichloromethane extraction procedure with ultratrace (ng/l) detection and quantitation by a gas chromatograph equipped with a tin-selective flame photometric detector (GC-FPD, ref. 9). All data are expressed as ng Sn/l.

The cells were washed (centrifugation at 6000 x g, 15 min, resuspension in artificial estuarine salts) and added to artificial estuarine salts¹⁶ (final cell concentration approximately 5 x 10⁸/ml) containing 100 µg/l tributyltin¹⁷. Incubation was at 22°C in 125 ml of the medium. Aliquots were removed periodically for GC-FPD analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Biodegradation studies

Surface water samples from industrially impacted (Baltimore Harbor) and marina (Annapolis) locations were distributed (800 ml) into 1.2 l bottles and a spike of a chromatographically purified aqueous tributyltin solution¹⁷ was added to give a final concentration of approximately 1 µg/l. Samples were incubated aerobically at in situ temperatures in the dark or under a bank of 40-w incandescent lamps. Aliquots were periodically removed for butyltins analysis using the above GC-FPD method. Autoclaved (121°C, 15 min) samples served as sterile controls.

Biodegradation experiments with pure cultures of tributyltin-resistant Chesapeake Bay bacteria were conducted with cells pregrown in Nelson medium¹⁶ plus 100 µg/l tributyltin.

Occurrence of tributyltin in Chesapeake Bay

Surface water samples from north and south portions of the Chesapeake Bay showed generally low (< 10 ng/l) levels of tributyltin species and undetectable levels of dibutyltin species (Table 2). Exceptions were samples from Annapolis and Little Ck. stations which showed elevated levels of di- and tributyltin species. Previous work in our laboratory^{8,9} has shown similar analytical results, with generally low levels of tributyltin detected in Baltimore Harbor and open Chesapeake Bay waters and elevated levels in Annapolis marina areas. Tetra- and monobutyltin species were not detected.

Unger, et al.¹⁰ detected butyltin species in Hampton Roads-Elizabeth R. area and York R. surface waters. Near Sarah Ck (York R.) marinas, tributyltin levels were elevated

TABLE 2

CONCENTRATIONS (ng Sn/l) OF BUTYLTIN SPECIES IN
CHESAPEAKE BAY SURFACE WATERS
(SEPT.-OCT., 1985)

Site	Bu ₂ Sn	Bu ₃ Sn
Jones Falls	ND ^a	2.5
Colgate Ck.	ND	2.6
Sparrows Pt.	ND	ND
Ft. McHenry	ND	3.6
Sandy Pt.	ND	ND
Annapolis	20	61
754	ND	5.1
735	ND	4.6
723	ND	2.3
707	ND	3.0
657	ND	3.8
652	ND	9.1
Little Ck.	16 (1.2) ^b	46 (5.0) ^b

^a not detected (< 2 ng/l). Neither monobutyltin (detection limit 20 ng/l) nor tetrabutyltin (detection limit 2 ng/l) species were detected.

^b standard deviation, triplicate samples

(19-66 ng Sn/l in summer). North and South Branches of the Elizabeth R. also contained elevated (16-26 ng Sn/l) tributyltin levels.¹⁰

Microbial resistance to butyltin species

The number of tributyltin resistant bacteria in the water column was studied by plate count methods. Preliminary work on 20 sites in Chesapeake Bay showed that less than 1% of the total viable count was resistant to 2 mg/l tributyltin in Nelson agar. The sole exception was the water sample from Little Ck., for which 40% of the counted microorganisms were resistant to tributyltin. In subsequent experiments, we compared samples from industrially-impacted Baltimore Harbor, and relatively "clean" sites in the eastern Bay. A higher percentage of tributyltin-resistant (1 mg/l) bacteria were found in eastern Bay waters (Table 3). Bacteria isolated from sediment samples gave mixed results with some Baltimore Harbor sites having appreciably higher levels of tributyltin-resistant bacteria.

However, these agar plate count experiments do not reflect the *in situ* toxicity of tributyltin to estuarine bacteria. Techniques such as [³H] thymidine incorporation or [¹⁴C] glutamate metabolism are more sensitive indicators of metal toxicity.¹⁸ Using these indicators, concentrations of tributyltin as low as 5 µg/l were found to be inhibitory to Chesapeake Bay microorganisms.¹⁸

TABLE 3

TRIBUTYLTIN RESISTANCE OF CHESAPEAKE BAY AEROBIC,
HETEROTROPHIC MICROORGANISMS

BALTIMORE HARBOR		% resistance	
		1 mg/l	10 mg/l
Jones Falls	water	2.4	0.2
	sed.	26.7	0
Colgate Ck.	water	11.5	0.2
	sed.	3.0	0.1
Sparrows Pt.	water	12.5	0.2
	sed.	25.6	0
Ft. McHenry	water	6.8	1.0
	sed.	4.5	0.4
EASTERN BAY			
Hollicott Noose	water	27.2	0
	sed.	1.8	0
Wades Pt.	water	38.9	0
	sed.	5.9	0
Choptank Mouth	water	37.5	0
	sed.	0	0

Tributyltin biodegradation

Biodegradation experiments were conducted on water samples from sites near industrial (Baltimore Harbor) and marina (Annapolis) activities in Chesapeake Bay. Samples were collected in February, spiked with tributyltin (1 µg/l), and incubated in the dark at *in situ* temperatures (5°C). Periodic GC-FPD analysis showed that no degradation of the tributyltin spike occurred, even after two weeks incubation (Figure 1). Mass balances (sum of all butyltin species) were > 90%. However, samples collected in early September and incubated at *in situ* temperatures (28°C) showed gradual decreases in tributyltin levels with increasing amounts of di- and monobutyltin species with time (Figure 2).

Under incandescent light the apparent degradation of tributyltin was more rapid (Figure 2), such that after six days only about half of the initial tributyltin tin spike was detected, with the combined di- and monobutyltin concentrations making up much of the decrease in tributyltin levels. Sterile controls showed only slight increases in di and monobutyltin species. Mass balances were > 85% in Annapolis samples and > 65% in Baltimore Harbor. The acceleration of tributyltin degradation under light suggests that photosynthetic microorganisms are important in environmental tributyltin degradation.

Representative chromatograms from the

February 5°C

1. Time course of butyltin speciation in samples of Chesapeake Bay water collected in February and spiked with approximately 1 µg Sn/l as tributyltin. Samples were incubated in the dark at 5°C and aliquots were periodically removed for butyltins analysis by GC-FPD. Samples were run in triplicate bottles. Error bars denote +/- one standard deviation of the mean.

biodegradation experiments (Annapolis samples) are shown in Figure 3. Also shown is the purity of the tributyltin research material¹⁷ used as a spike in these experiments.

Similar results were obtained in water samples collected in late September (23°C) and spiked with tributyltin (0.3 µg/l, final concentration). After one week, approximately 25-35% of the tributyltin had been degraded to dibutyltin in both Baltimore and Annapolis samples. Under incandescent lamps the degradation rates increased slightly in Baltimore Harbor samples and substantially in Annapolis samples. After one week, about 50% of the tributyltin was degraded to dibutyltin in the light-incubated Annapolis samples. Mass balances were > 80% for both sites. These results are similar to those of Lee et al.¹⁹ who employed *in situ* incubations of samples of San Diego Bay waters. They found half-lives of 1-2 weeks for tributyltin, with degradation to di- and monobutyltin species.

During the early September degradation experiments certain samples from both Annapolis

(Figure 3) and Baltimore Harbor showed the presence of tetrabutyltin (trace to 0.3 µg/l concentrations). The identity of tetrabutyltin was confirmed by GC-mass spectrometry. Tetrabutyltin occurrence was sporadic, usually occurring in only one of the duplicate samples. However, tetrabutyltin was observed only in light incubated samples and not in sterile samples incubated in the light. This suggests involvement of photosynthetic microorganisms in tetrabutyltin production, possibly via a redistribution reaction with tributyltin. We have detected tetrabutyltin in surface micro-layer and drydock samples⁹. The origin of tetrabutyltin in these samples is unclear and could also be attributed to impurities in tributyltin antifouling paints.

Two unidentified peaks appeared in chromatograms from the Annapolis water samples during

September 28°C

2. Time course of butyltin speciation in summertime collected Chesapeake Bay water collected in early September, spiked with tributyltin, and incubated at 28°C under light (40-w incandescent lamps) or dark conditions. Tetrabutyltin occurred sporadically in some of these samples but is not shown in the figure (see text). Concentrations shown are means of duplicate samples.

3. Representative chromatograms from time course biodegradation experiments shown in Figure 2. Production of mono- and dibutyltin species along with two unidentified peaks occurs with time under incandescent light incubation. A small amount of degradation occurs in sterile controls. An aqueous tributyltin research material¹⁷ (bottom) was used to spike the samples. Dipropyltin was used as an internal standard.

the course of the biodegradation experiment (Figure 3). The peaks appear between monobutyl and dibutyltin (retention time 3.61 min) and di- and tributyltin (retention time 6.75 min). The latter peak also appeared in the sterile control at a lower concentration. Whether these peaks represent additional tributyltin degradation products, methylated mono- and dibutyltin species, or perhaps non-tin containing molecules (i.e. sulfur containing species) is uncertain at present. The peaks were not seen in chromatograms from dark-incubated samples. Tributyltin degradation

experiments with pure cultures of algae are underway to identify these products.

Experiments using pure cultures of tributyltin-resistant bacteria from Chesapeake Bay (Tables 2,3) have shown little or no degradation of tributyltin added (100 µg/l, final concentration) to cultures of these organisms. It seems that biodegradation of tributyltin is not a common mechanism of resistance in tributyltin-resistant estuarine bacteria.

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